

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION OF STUDENTS

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Annotation: This article presents the purpose of independent education, autonomy and cooperation characteristics of independent education, independent thinking and theoretical views of world scientists on independent education.

Key words: Independent education, independent thinking, goal, knowledge, competence, competence, competence, innovation, teacher-pedagogue, student, educational process.

Currently, in our Republic, at all stages of the educational system, including in higher education, a number of priorities are being implemented, all measures necessary to improve the quality and efficiency of education, to guarantee its effectiveness. Implementation of modern approaches to organizing independent education of students in the educational process (systematic, innovative, competency, informative), application of innovative, digital technologies, modern information technologies, excellent study of foreign languages in order to establish the use of the experience of advanced foreign countries in this field, qualimetric assessment of educational results, as well as on the basis of – students) such issues as assessing the results of their activities (pedagogical process) in a qualimetric way, determining their quality by designing perspective plans for making changes to it are important tasks in the responsibility of any educational institution. As a result of the implementation of these tasks, educational institutions are put before them - the quality of the educational process, which is organized in order to fulfill state and social orders, the organization and management of educational cognitive activity of learners, the purposeful Organization of pedagogical activity of the teacher, and leads to the realization of identity in education (correspondence of the result with.

The main purpose of the student's independent education (TMT) is to systematize and strengthen the learned theoretical knowledge, practical skills, deepen and expand theoretical knowledge, develop psychological and pedagogical skills, form competencies (private and professional), form skills for working with regulatory, legal documents, data and special literature. Taking into account that independent education is guided by the individual himself, with this activity a person can freely and at any time choose from sources himself, using it from the point of view of purpose, means, content [1].

Independent education is both autonomous and cooperative in nature. Autonomy in obtaining independent knowledge is the ability to identify and select teaching goals, principles, content, methods and tools, to carry them out without difficulty and without the help of external influence. Collaborative independent learning, on the other hand, occurs in more small groups, in the team conducting independent activities in the process of finding a solution to a single problem together [2]. Independent education is inextricably linked with the concept of independent thinking. At this point, it is also worth citing the definition given to this concept: "independent thinking is the mental activity of a person, which consists in independently solving problems facing him at the level of his intellectual capabilities, using various ways, methods, means, relying on his knowledge and life experiences, setting goals and objectives." The formation of skills for performing independent work in young people can be carried out in the training of various educational subjects. For example, in accordance with the content of Science, the content of independent work on the subject of general pedagogy is understood as a time when students are directed to the active organization of their independent activities, the fulfillment of didactic goals set before them and are specially allocated for this.

R.X.The "dictionary of pedagogical terms", written under the leadership of Djurayev, defines the concept of "Independent Education" as "the process of a person's personal actions aimed at studying the experience of generations, the achievements of Science and technology with the help of tools and literature of his choice" [3] – J. In khasanbayev's "Explanatory Dictionary of pedagogical science", however, "Independent Education "was viewed as" a form of study aimed at strengthening the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications, studying additional material " [4].

P.Q.According to husanbayev's definition, independent education is a systematic activity aimed at the formation of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and competencies based on independent mastering of educational materials, tasks with varying degrees of complexity, creative and independent performance of practical tasks in the audience and outside the audience [4] .

Another description of Independent Education is V.One can find in Okon's work:" Independent Education is such a type of teaching that purpose, content, circumstances and Means depend on the subject himself " [5]. In this approach, it is possible to distinguish three main situations related to the activities of the subject: the purpose, content and means of teaching. A.P.Pshebelsky and M.I.In the opinion of zaborshikova, "independent education is the process of a

pedagogue's practical activities at school, purposeful, planned and continuous independent work in order to raise his professional production.”

T.A.Ilyushova noted that “independent education is one of the forms of gaining professional production of an educator.” It is a goal-oriented work of an educator to expand and deepen his theoretical knowledge, and requires the improvement and application of new professional skills and qualifications based on the modern requirements of pedagogy and psychology. T.A. Ilyushova and G.A.Zheleznyakova talks about the peculiarities of Independent Education in teaching a foreign language in higher educational institutions that do not specialize in the language [6]. At the same time, the concepts of “Independent Education”, “independent reading”, “independent work” are used as synonyms in scientific and educational literature. Based on the analysis of research and literature conducted, independent education and independent work in our opinion were described as follows: “Independent Education is a process of educational activity built on the basis of independent study of a task (issue, problem) with or without the help of a specialist (in the process of working on assignments, refrains, article, thesis preparation, course and graduation qualification work, independent.

In conclusion, it is not for nothing that teaching in a credit-modular system in higher education institutions pays special attention to the Independent Education of students. The educational process in higher education institutions includes not only lectures, seminars and laboratory classes on the main content of education and practical preparation for professional activities, but also independent education. Professional training, of course, regularly implies Independent Education. Therefore, when it is noted that independent education in the curriculum and science programs is one of the important conditions for obtaining basic, fundamental education, the Independent Education of students changes qualitatively.

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